

“LEARNING ENGLISH THROUGH ACTIONS”

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Annotation: The research based on the use of strategies, activities, and games on teaching vocabulary for pupils. Motivation is one of the most important thing on teaching language.

Keywords: Teaching, vocabulary, motivation, game, strategy, method.

INTRODUCTION

There are many learning strategies, and this study focuses on game strategy to motivate students to memorize new words and improve their vocabulary skills by the use of implementing vocabulary games. In fact, motivation is considered one of the essential factors in language learning. Motivated learners have a high motivation, it is a better chance of learning vocabulary successfully; so, unmotivated pupils will have a lesser chance of success. Therefore, in order to enhance learners' learning vocabulary, they need to be motivated by playing a game, to do activities, to complete some the task, and with relaxing achieved, learning the lexis increase smoothly (Moon, 2000) ¹⁰⁸.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

In the field of learning English language, many factors affect the pupils' knowledge level such as pupils' learning styles teachers' personality and teaching styles, students' background and teachers capacity of teaching and so on. Result of research, it has been identified that one of the most difficult problems of unsuccessful English education to grades 7-9 in secondary schools is that the pupils are demotivated to learn new vocabulary. Thus, having limited vocabulary knowledge students are not capable to express and speak well. Granowsky (2002) He marks that: many researchers have classified the important of vocabulary knowledge plays for students comprehensive reading, and for their school success and future education. For these

¹⁰⁸Moon,J (2000).Children learning English. London: Macmillan.

Reasons, the main goal of this research to generally explore pupils' vocabulary learning strategies and to assess, in particular, the effectiveness of game strategy to motivate the pupils.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Teachers' Strategies for learning vocabulary

The role of the teachers plays a main factor of glossary to find in learning strategies and to learn how students adopt these strategies effectively. Therefore, the focus of this research is to evaluate which vocabulary strategies the pupils use effectively and how it will help teachers to design their lesson plans and to construct practical instructions efficiently support pupils' competence in the class.

How to play Vocabulary games in School.

Teaching and learning words are carried on through methods we are familiar with; the teacher organizes learning, i.e. in the acquisition of information about a new word, it's form, meaning and usage; in drill and transformation to form lexical habits; in making use of the lexical in hearing, speaking and reading, or in language skills. Various techniques used to attain the goal – to fix the words in pupils' memory ready to use whenever they need them.

Presentation of new words.

Since every word has it's form, meaning, and usage to present, a word means to introduce to pupils it's forms and to explain it's meaning and usage. The techniques of teaching students the pronunciation and spelling of a word are as follows ¹⁰⁹.

- (1) Pure or conscious imitation;
- (2) Analogy;
- (3) Transcription;
- (4) Rules of reading since a word consists of sounds it heard or spoken and letter sit read or written the teacher shows the pupils how to pronounce, to read, and write it.

1. Psychological factors:

A) Pupils' age: the young pupils are the better is the chance for the use of redirect way. Pupils' intelligence: the brighter child the more direct the way.

2. Pedagogical factors:

A) The stage of teaching (junior, intermediate, senior)

B) The size of the class in overcrowded classes the translation is preferable because it's economical from the standpoint of time required for presentation, so more time is left for pupils to do exercises in using the word ¹¹

¹⁰⁹ Farida, D; Isrina, H, D & Apsari, Y. (2019). The implementation of Flash Cards To Improve Students' vocabulary Mastery. Project (Professional Journal Of English Education), 2 (3), 352 – 357.

C) The time allotted to learning the new words; when the teacher is pressed for time, he turns to the translation;

D) The qualifications of the teacher: the use of the direct way requires much still on the part of the teacher. The direct way is usually a success provided the teacher could skillfully apply audio – visual aids and verbal means.

3. Linguistic factors

A) Abstract or concrete notions: For conveying the meaning of abstract notions, the translation is preferable.

B) Extent (range) of meaning in comparison with that of the target language: In cases where range of meaning of a word does not coincide in the mother tongue and in, target language the translation interpretation should use. The assimilation gained through performing various exercises, which allow the pupils to acquire lexical habits. Teachers should also consider games that are appropriate to pupils' age, cultural background and interests, and teacher should as well consider activities where pupils can experience success. It's worthwhile to mention that game learning strategy also used for high school students. During the game pupils were able to understand and produce new language. They were also aware of the need to memorize vocabulary, articles, and prepositions. In summary, games are useful and effective tool that should applied in vocabulary classes

¹¹⁰ Sary, L. E.,& Sutobo, D (2018). The Effectiveness Of Vocabulary Self – Collection And Word Mapping Strategies For Teaching Vocabulary To Maritime With High And Low Metacognitive Awareness. English Education Journal, 8 (1), 35 – 42.

CONCLUSION

This is an exciting time to be teaching English as a second or foreign language. The spread of English around the world has created a growing need for qualified teachers – native and nonnative speakers. In many countries, children are starting to learn English at an ever – younger age. There is need who can deal with English in the workplace as well. The ever – growing use of varieties of English require careful linguistic description and appropriate pedagogies. One more important thing that, the pupils' interest and attitude to learning language is also up to the teachers tactics and the method which is chosen appropriately by teacher.

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